

**IMPACTS OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY
(ICT)-DRIVEN PEDAGOGY ON PERFORMANCE OF SSII IN
GEOMETRY IN SOME SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN GOMBE
LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA**

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to our families; Ali Ahmadu, Fatima Muhammad, Habiba Isah Muhammad (Akmal), Na'amadu Bako, Aishatu Shu'aibu, and Abubakar Adamu, for their love, care and support during the course of our study.

DECLARATION

We hereby declared that this project was conducted and written by us and has not been presented in any previous application for a degree. All sources of information are duly acknowledged by means of reference.

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APPROVAL PAGE

The project entitled “IMPACTS OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT)-DRIVEN PEDAGOGY ON PERFORMANCE OF SSII IN GEOMETRY IN SOME SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN GOMBE LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA” by Ali Bello Ahmadu and Na’amadu Maryam Bako, has partially fulfilled the requirement for the award of the degree of BSc. (Ed) Mathematics of Gombe State University, Gombe.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the Impacts of Information Communication Technology (ICT)-driven pedagogy on performance of SS II in Geometry in some selected secondary schools n Gombe local government area. The study, which adopted an experimental design and a pretest, posttest in nature with have two classes assigned, one to control group and the other to experimental group in two schools as a fair representation of 16 schools comprising of 14230 students within the metropolis of Gombe on the basis that the school was one of those that have well equipped computer laboratory. The sample groups consisted of 20 SSII students with 11 boys and 9 girls .The data generated using the instrument, Geometry Performance Test (GPT) which comprised of 10 items validated by experts (in the Faculty of Education) and subsequently pilot tested for reliability. Random probability sampling was also used to select the participants in each of the SS2 classes of the selected schools to form a group. Mathematics pre-test and post-test questions was set up by the researchers based on the curriculum of the schools on geometry. After the intervention, the Experimental group had outdone the Control group in the post-test and the experimental group significantly gained more than the control group. This study recommends that government should provide adequate ICT facilities in all levels of education as it might enhance learning and Mathematics teachers should be encouraged to use ICT-driven pedagogy when teaching geometry topics.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Problem

Mathematics is perceived by society as the foundation for scientific and technological knowledge that is cherished by societies worldwide. It is an instrument for political, socio-economic, scientific and technological developments (Githua & Mwangi, 2003). This explains why mathematics is a compulsory subject for all learners in primary and secondary schools as specified in the National Policy on Education by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2006). Mathematics is also used by Tertiary institutions as a basic entry requirement of students who want to enroll in any program of their choice to select secondary school learners for entry into degree programs.

Mathematics without doubt remains very important to all disciplines and fields of human work and study (Odili, 2006). It has continued to play significant role in the development of both the individuals and nations. Mathematics is also a fundamental science that is needed for the understanding of most fields in the sciences and technological education. Therefore, Mathematics is a necessary tool needed to be able to function effectively in the present technological age (Aremu, 1998). According to Abakpa and Iji (2011) teaching and learning of mathematics consistently generate interest among scholars over the years. Mathematics is an intellectually stimulating subject that

affects every talent of human activities such as politics, economics science and technology. It is the model by which scientific concepts are understood and bedrock for understanding and applying technologies.

Geometry as a basic and one of the most important branches of mathematics is the study of size, shape and position of 2-dimensional shapes and 3-dimensional figures. There are many interesting and sometimes surprising results in geometry that can stimulate students. Presenting it in a way that stimulates curiosity encourages exploration that can support learners' intuition; thus enhancing communication, students' learning and interest in mathematics. This would further encourage students to discuss problems in geometry, articulate their ideas and develop clearly structured arguments, skills and recognition of the importance of proofs in mathematics (Tsoho, 2011). As important as this aspect of mathematics is however, students' achievement in this area has not been encouraging. For instance, the report of the Chief Examiners of the West African Examination Council (WAEC) for 2005 had shown that many students avoided or skipped answering certain questions especially those involving geometry in the SSCE. Another study conducted at the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Abuja investigated the effect of mathematical games and simulations on Senior Secondary School Students' interest in Geometry (Jorind 2012), found that students who were taught using

games and simulations technique gain more interest in the learning of geometry than their counterparts taught using Conventional Teachers Method, CTM.

The Nigerian Mathematics curriculum comprises of many topics, including Geometry which is taught from primary to secondary levels. It is regarded as “a unifying topic to the entire Mathematics curriculum and it is a rich source of visualization for arithmetical, algebraic, and statistical concepts” (Idris, 2009). Sub-topics covered under Geometry at the senior secondary level include geometrical terms and relationships, geometrical constructions, symmetry, angle properties and locus. However, performance in Geometry has been poor (Idris and Myers, 2009) pointing out that little regard has been given to how well the learners understand geometrical concepts.

Also, Kurumeh (2007) opined that generally, students fear and hate mathematics which results to lack of interest and poor achievement in mathematics particularly geometry and menstruation. Studies on the factors responsible for this poor achievement have identified poor teaching methods and non-usage of instructional materials among others (Badmus, 2002; Harbor-Peters, 2002 & Iji, 2005). Most teachers adopt the conventional approach to teaching. The conventional approach is a traditional approach to teaching, whereby the teacher disseminates the information verbally to the students. Sometimes, the teacher writes on the chalkboard while the students listen and

take notes and ask questions for clarifications. In the conventional approach, the teacher is in charge of the entire environment and serves as the decision maker. Students are regarded as having 'vacuums' to be filled by the teacher; who is believed to make learning possible. Learning is quite competitive, area of coverage is considered important and knowledge is mastered by students through drill and practice. The curriculum is regarded as absolute and teachers hardly tamper with it even when it is obvious that students do not understand some concepts. Rather than adapting the curriculum to meet the needs of the students, those who have difficulties are viewed as slow learners. In this approach, according to Ogbonna (2003), curricular activities rely mainly on textbooks and workbooks. Students are viewed as just waiting for information from the teacher.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been used to deliver instruction in some countries around the world, such as Malaysia (Myers, 2009) and USA (Idris, 2009). Nigeria is said to have a policy document known as National ICT policy which commenced in earnest 1980's as computer policy. And later from the year 2001, it was National policy on Information Technology and currently the National ICT policy by the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Some of the specific areas from the policy are as follows. (Sulaiman 2018).

- i. Making the use of ICT mandatory at the basic, post-basic and tertiary education level.
- ii. Development of curricular for primary, secondary and tertiary institutions.
- iii. Use ICT in distance education such as distance learning program.
- iv. Training the trainer scheme for the NYSC corps members. Etc

There are several ICT driven pedagogies, of which Teaching for Understanding (TFU) (Blythe, 1997), Understanding by Design (UbD) (Wiggins and McTighe, 2005), and Project-based Learning (PbL) (Moursund, 1999) are the most common approaches used in delivering instruction. This study used UbD from Wiggins and McTighe (2005), since it focuses on deliberately planning the learning experience, instruction and acceptable evidence of competency in the outcomes and results (assessment). From the perspective of UbD teaching approach, teaching should focus on understanding the learning content through designing more effective learning content and assessments (Wiggins, & McTighe, 2005). Learners should be taught using pictures, symbols and concrete objects for them to be able to recognize, observe and identify their properties (Bruner, 1960). In addition, Geometer's Sketchpad (GSP) can be used to improve learners' performance in Geometry (Myers, 2009).

Studies conducted by Kanandjebo (2017) at Omusati Education region, Namibia, on the effect of ICT-driven pedagogy on Grade 12 learners revealed that, there was a statistically significant difference between the two groups (Control group and Experimental group) in terms of learner performance on Geometry topics. It implies that the use of ICT-driven pedagogy improved learners' performance. Positive attitude toward ICT-driven pedagogy by learners translated into learners encouraging for the adoption of ICT-driven pedagogy.

Therefore, based on the above, we want to conduct our research on the impacts of information and communication technology (ICT)-driven pedagogy on performance of SS2 students in geometry in some selected secondary schools in Gombe local government.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Kanandjebo (2017) stated that despite significant researches using innovative strategies in the teaching and learning of mathematics, students' performance in mathematics is still low especially in the aspects of geometry. Therefore, there is need for more simulation as an approach to the teaching of geometry so as to improve students' performance in mathematics particularly in the area of geometry.

1.3 Purpose and Specific objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effects of ICT-driven pedagogy on SS2 students' performance in geometry in some selected secondary schools in Gombe local government area.

Specifically, this study aims to:

- i. Determine the background knowledge of Senior Secondary School students in Geometry prior to the treatment
- ii. Find out the effect of ICT-Driven pedagogy on Senior Secondary School students' academic achievement in geometry
- iii. Determine the mean gain of Senior Secondary School Students in Geometry after the treatment

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to address the problems

- i. What is the background knowledge of Senior Secondary School students in Geometry both experimental and control group prior to the treatment?
- ii. What is the effect of ICT-Driven pedagogy on Senior Secondary School students' (experimental group) academic achievement in geometry?
- iii. What is the mean gain of Senior Secondary School Students in Geometry after the treatment?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study

H₀₁: There is no significant difference of in the mean academics performance of both experimental and control group at pretest (prior to the treatment)

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean academics performance of experimental group at pretest and post-test (After the treatment).

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the mean academics performance of both Experimental and control group at post-test (After the treatment).

1.6 Significance of the study

1. Secondary school mathematics teachers as it will shed light on the benefits of the use of ICT-driven teaching approach as well as inform educators on how effective the ICT-driven pedagogy is in improving students' achievement in geometry. The findings of this study may exist as a source of literature in this area and provide valuable insight into the successful teaching of Geometry using ICT.
2. The study might also inform mathematics teachers about the appropriate teaching strategies to utilize in order to enhance understanding of Geometrical terms and relationships, angle properties and symmetry.
3. Research students will utilize the findings of this study as a source of literature in this area and provide valuable insight into the successful teaching of Geometry using ICT. And to help build a foundation of their

study, demonstrate how their study advances knowledge, conceptualize their study assess the appropriate research design and instrumentation in experimental research of this kind.

1.7 Scope and Limitations of the study

This study was conducted in some few selected secondary schools in Gombe local government area only due to limited time and lack of enough ICT-driven instructional gadgets. It was also been based on a part of mathematics (Geometry) only due to the same reason above.

1.8 Definition of terms

Key terms to be use in this research should be understood as follows:

(a) Geometry topics refer to the three themes taught in this study, i.e., geometrical terms and relationships, geometrical symmetry and angle properties. Geometry and Geometry topics were used interchangeably and had a similar meaning.

(b) Geometers Simulator (GS), Geometry software program that allows learners and educators to create and manipulate shapes and to study Geometry in greater detail. In this study GS is defined the same way.

(c) ICT-driven Pedagogy (IDP) refers to the teaching approach that involves the use of technological tools to either deliver the learning content or assist with teaching the learning content.

(d) Information and Communication Technology (ICT) refers to all the technologies used for the handling and communication of information and their use specifically in education (Ministry of Education, 2005). In the context of this study, ICT refers to technologies such as GSP software, YouTube and so on that was used to deliver instructions in order to improve teaching and learning.

(e) Performance is the academic accomplishment of a given task measured against pre-defined known standards of accuracy, completeness and speed (Cobb, 2005). In this study it refers to the Geometry test scores or marks of SS2 Mathematics learners.

(f) Performance ruling in this study refers to pass or fail in the pretest and posttest.

(h) Experimental Group are the population of students to be taught using the ICT-driven approach.

(i) Control Group are the population of students to be taught using the traditional approach.

(j) Geometers' Sketchpad (GSP), according to Myers (2009), is a dynamic Geometry software programme that allows learners and educators to create and manipulate shapes and to study Geometry in greater detail. In this study GSP is defined the same way.

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This chapter reviews the literature related to the study. It reviews previous works based on the variables of the study. The chapter started by the theoretical frame work of the study, Bruner's constructivist theory, followed by the conceptual reviews of the study, followed by computer games for mathematics, followed by traditional teaching method, followed by ICT-driven pedagogy (understanding by design), followed by perception of learners on ICT driven pedagogy, and finally the chapter reviews empirical review of the study.

2.1 Theoretical Framework of the Study

The study adopted Bruner's (1960) Constructivist Theory and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989). Constructivist-based learning environments are characterized by problem-solving activities, provision of stimulating learning environments, cooperative learning and the promotion of learning through exploration (Roblyer, Edwards, & Havriluk, 2010). Constructivists believe that knowledge is not transmitted but constructed in an individual's mind by participating in certain experiences. Bruner's (1960) Constructivist Theory states that learning is an active process in which learners construct new ideas or concepts based upon existing knowledge. According to Bruner (1960), the learning content should be structured in considerable detail that

enables learners to easily grasp the information. UbD teaching approaches was drawn from learning theories that focus on transformational learning (Clayton, 2011).

UbD supports authentic tasks and calls for teaching for understanding, with emphasis on problem-based learning and the use of pictorial and symbolic activities. TAM focuses on an individual's perceived ease of use and perceived use, meanwhile the Theory of flow focuses on the learners' satisfaction and attitudes as discussed earlier. Therefore, if the level of flow is high and teachers are applying UbD teaching approach which is based on Bruner's Constructivist Theory ideas, learners might perform better in school subjects.

2.1.1 Bruner's Constructivist Theory

Bruner's Constructivist Theory stipulates that learners are active problem-solvers and capable of exploring 'difficult subjects' provided that the learning content is structured and presented in sequential order (Bruner, 1960). Bruner refers to the structure of knowledge as a relationship among factual elements and teaching and learning techniques. Thus, structure implies various teaching mechanisms that will enable the learners most readily to grasp the learning content.

Bruner (1960) believes that children go through three stages of intellectual development:

1. *Enactive stage* - Refers to learning through actions. This goes in line with McLeod (2008), for whom knowledge largely takes the form of motor responses. Learners may be able to perform a physical task better than describing the same task that has just been presented.
2. *Iconic stage* - Refers to the use of pictures or models. It is vital that teachers use diagrams and illustrations to accompany verbal information.
3. *Symbolic stage* - Refers to the development of the ability to think in abstract terms. Knowledge is mostly in the form of arbitrary words, mathematical symbols and other symbol systems (McLeod, 2008).

Bruner (1960) recommended the combined use of three modes of representation of learning, that are, concrete, pictorial and symbolic, which will lead to more effective learning and good performance in school subjects. He added that instruction should incorporate relevant learning materials that will facilitate interest towards learning. Thus, when pictures and/or symbols are used in the presentation of the learning content, most of the learners' senses are involved and so improve learners' understanding.

Constructivists view learning as a process that occurs “when an individual constructs both mechanisms for learning and his or her own unique version of knowledge, colored by background, experiences, and aptitudes” (Roblyer, 2006, p.37). According to Retallick, Cocklin and Coombe (1998), constructivism

transforms learners from passive recipients of knowledge to active learners in the learning process, in most cases guided by the teacher. Learners construct their knowledge actively rather than just absorbing it from the teacher or the textbook.

Learners generate new knowledge through activities, experiences, and experiments. In addition, Rogers (2003) stated that the primary goal of the Constructivist Learning Theory is to help learners to learn how to learn.

In terms of technology, Bruner's Constructivist Theory advised that, teachers should use videos to equip learners with basic skills (Uriarte, & Uriarte, 2013). This will broaden their understanding of certain topics and motivate them to learn, which will in turn lead to better performance. Teachers should provide opportunities for learners to construct new knowledge and meaning from authentic experiences (Uriarte, & Uriarte, 2013). In addition, Bruner (1960) emphasized that education should develop symbolic thinking of learners. Therefore, the use of GSP and other ICT tools can be used in teaching Geometry to enable a learner to grasp Geometry concepts with ease.

2.2 Conceptual Reviews of the study

This section reviews the conceptual frame works related to this study such as;

2.2.1 Computer Games for Mathematics

There are several studies that report on the use of commercial computer games for mathematics, or present the development and evaluation of instructional games designed for the specific subject. As indicated by the following review of relevant studies, computer games can increase students' math achievement and performance, and promote positive attitudes towards mathematics. For instance, in a recent study, Pareto et al. (2011), created a teachable-agent arithmetic game that aims in training basic arithmetic skills. The game was evaluated in a study with 153 participants, consisting of 3rd (JS3) and 5th (SS2) grade students. The results indicate that the game helped students improve their math performance and self-efficacy beliefs. Ahmad and Latih (2010) describe the development of an educational math game on fractions for primary school students.

Similarly, Lee (2009) report on the creation and evaluation of an education game on fractions and mention that it improved students' understanding and performance. Concerning the use of commercial games for mathematics, Zavaleta et al. (2005) suggest in their study that the use of a commercial game for elementary school algebra enhanced students' achievement. Kebritchi, Hirumi, and Bai (2010) investigated the impact of commercial math games on 193 high school students' math performance, with positive results concerning the student's perception of mathematics, motivation, and achievement.

Ke and Grabowski (2007) examined the effects of the use of adventure games on 125, 5th (SS2) grade students that were assigned to three groups: cooperative game playing group, competitive game playing group, and no game playing group. According to their findings, after the four-week intervention the two game playing groups had better math performance, while the cooperative game playing group had better attitude towards the subject, compared to the other conditions.

In another study, Ke (2008) examined the effects of the use of computer games on 4th and 5th grade students that were enrolled in a five-week summer math program, with positive results concerning the students' attitude towards math. More recently, Kim and Chang (2010) performed regression analyses using 170,000, 4th (SS1) grade students, demonstrating that math computer games had a positive effect on male minority students.

Other studies focus on the use of math computer games for the remediation of specific deficits, such as dyscalculia. For example, Wilson, A. J., Revkin, S. K., Cohen, D., Cohen, L. and Dehaene, S. (2006) created an adaptive computer game for dyscalculia and tested it in a five-week evaluation study with nine children with math learning difficulties. The results indicated an increase in the children's math performance on core number sense tasks, as well as an improvement as regards their confidence in their mathematical abilities. Regarding any pertinent research

projects, the E-GEMS (Electronic Games for Education in Math and Science) project contributed on the development of various educational games that increased student engagement and achievement, and produced several design heuristics (Klawe & Phillips, 1995).

2.2.2 Basic Features of Educational Games

Instructional designers should try to create intrinsically motivating educational environments that would help students learn in an effortless and engaging way. Computer games, in particular, contain the following three elements that make them so interesting, and can be used in order to motivate the learner: challenge, fantasy, and curiosity (Malone, 1980). Malone (1980) draws upon these observations in order to develop a set of guidelines for the design of effective and motivational instructional computer games. In accordance with these guidelines, games should have clear goals, uncertain outcomes, feedback, and gradually increasing difficulty levels. Furthermore, they should contain curiosity and fantasy elements, such as emotional aspects. Moreover, they should respond in an appropriate way to the players' actions, and they should provide them with choice over various environmental aspects (Malone, 1980).

Hays (2005) reports on these heuristics, and suggests a set of design recommendations for educational games, emphasizing on the instructional quality these games should have. More specifically, the game should be integrated into a

larger educational program, and it should also incorporate elements that help students build new knowledge structures or complete their existing ones (Hays, 2005). Furthermore, as stated by Fisch (2005), the appropriate incorporation of educational content into the game is a key factor in the design of effective instructional games. Students should also be provided with offline material and resources that could add to the game's educational value, as well as support and guidance by teachers and parents (Fisch, 2005). Prensky (2001), points out some features that engaging games have; these are the following: objectives, opposition, interaction, representation, and outcomes. Similarly, Kiili (2005) proposes an experiential gaming model based on Csikszentmihalyi's flow theory and experiential learning principles; this model can be used for the design, analysis and evaluation of educational computer games. The above design guidelines and basic features of instructional games were taken into consideration in the design of the proposed game.

2.2.3 Traditional Teaching Method

The traditional or the conventional method of teaching is a teacher-centered approach, where the teacher plays an active role and the student passive role in the learning process (Tumba, Chinda, & Andeyarka, 2014). It is also referred to as the "chalk and talk" method of teaching (Jackson, 2012). Traditional teaching lesson presentation involves the use of discussions and explanations using a chalkboard.

Based on the study conducted by Keùan and Çaliùkan (2013) on the effect of learning Geometry topics with Geometer's sketchpad; 18 the researchers used Wilcoxon signed-rank test to examine the difference between the scores of retention test and post-test of the group that was taught using traditional methods. Further, Keùan and Çaliùkan (2013) found traditional method to have had effects on retention and performance ($z = 0.402$; $\rho > 0.05$). Learners who were taught using traditional methods performed poorly compared to those that were taught using GSP. In this study, a traditional teaching method was used to teach the Control group.

Despite the benefits of Mathematics to our day-to-day activities and as an agent of nation's development and wealth creation, students interest in the learning of mathematics has not been favorable due to certain factors such as students' background, learning environment, non-utilization of viable instructional strategies among others (Nkwo, 2003).

Mathematics has been described by Uzema (2016) as a dynamic and elegant field of human creation and a strong binding force among various branches of sciences, without which knowledge of science often remain superficial. It is a subject which deals with numbers and figures. Mathematics is used throughout our lives. The National Mathematics Advisory Panel (NMAP, 2008) holds that mathematics is used throughout our daily lives. The importance of mathematics in

day-to-day activities is no longer news. However, what remains news is the fact that students' academic performance in mathematics has not improved significantly in Kano State and Nigeria as a whole (Abdul, 2015). Numerous factors were identified by some researchers for the poor academic performance in mathematics by students, some of which included: shortage of qualified mathematics teachers, poor facilities, equipment and instructional materials for effective teaching (Yemi & Adeshina, 2013).

Mathematics education in Kano State and the entire country, Nigeria, has persistently been experiencing one form of problem or the other, particularly in relation to the general poor academic performances of secondary school students (Adebule, 2012). Adebule observed that, such academic problems include students' unparalleled hatred, indifference, test anxiety and poor attitude towards mathematics, teachers' dissatisfaction, and poor environment, non-availability of appropriate textbooks and poor methods of teaching. Quite remarkably, most of the secondary school students in Kano State developed mathematics anxiety as a result of ineffective teaching methods by teachers (Adebule, 2012).

In addition to the above, Abdullahi (2012) opined that despite the fact that Mathematics is the bedrock of scientific and technological developments of the country, a compulsory subjects in both Junior and Senior levels of Secondary School education and a basic requirement for gaining admission into tertiary

institutions, the performance of secondary school students in examinations, most especially West Africa School Certificate Examination (WASCE) and National Examination Council (NECO) is alertly poor in Gombe state and this is a great concern to both teachers, educators, parents government and all other stake holders in education in the state.

In spite of the important role that Mathematics plays in many fields of work, there has traditionally been poor performance in the subject at national examination level in some countries globally (Ali, 2013; Karue, & Amukowa, 2013); some of the contributory three (3) factors being poor teaching methods, lack of proper instructional materials and lack of learners' involvement when teaching (Ali, 2013; Karue, & Amukowa, 2013; Haimbodi, 2012; Naukushu, 2011; Mateya, 2008).

Despite the fact that Mathematics is the bedrock of scientific and technological developments of the country, a compulsory subjects in both Junior and Senior levels of Secondary School education and a basic requirement for gaining admission into tertiary institutions, the performance of secondary school students in examinations, most especially West Africa School Certificate Examination (WASCE) and National Examination Council (NECO) is alertly poor and this is a great concern to both teachers, educators, parents government and all other stake holders in education. In general, reasons for such persistent poor

performance in the subject by the secondary school students have been traced to poor teaching method, attitude of students towards the subject, school- size and location, gender-difference of the students, teachers-variables, government, lack of motivation in teachers, students' level of mental development, etc. Abdullahi S. M. (2012).

2.2.4 ICT-driven Pedagogy: Understanding by Design (UbD)

The UbD framework was developed by Wiggins and McTighe (1998) as a planning framework to guide curriculum, assessment and instruction. It focuses on teaching for understanding through designing more effective learning content and assessments. This framework capitalises on assessment tasks which learners should use to construct new knowledge and those that require an extended time to complete (Marzano, Pickering, & McTighe, 1993). Anwaruddin (2013) supports Marzano et al.'s (1993) claim that assessment tasks that require an extended time, deepen learners' understanding since they are actively engaged. Consequently, these assessment tasks will increase learners' motivation and interest level in subjects.

UbD places more emphasis on teachers as designers of learning, and works within the standards-driven curriculum to help them clarify learning goals, devise revealing assessments of learners' understanding, and craft effective and engaging learning activities (McTighe, & Wiggins, 2012). Under this framework, learning

outcomes and assessment are gathered before specifying instructional procedures in order to enhance learners' understanding during lesson presentation (Anwaruddin, 2013). McTighe and Wiggins (2012) stated that UbD calls for collaborative learning, use of technology and other teaching approaches in order to design, share, and critique learning content. It differs from conventional thinking about teaching and learning as it emphasizes the use of a backward design process (Social Studies Center for Educator Development (SSCED), 1999). In this study, the Experimental Group was taught using the UbD approach.

This study used the UbD lesson plan format in preparation of the lessons and assessment to test the Experimental Group's understanding of Geometrical concepts. Learners in both groups were encouraged to be active learners in order to enhance their understanding during lessons and to collaborate in order to share ideas (Johnson, Johnson, & Holubec, 2008) during class activities.

2.3 Study based on ICT-driven Pedagogy

In a study conducted by Kanandjebo (2017) on the effects of ICT-driven pedagogy found that there was a statistically significant difference between the two groups (dependent variables and independent variables) in terms of learner performance on geometry topics. This implies that the use of ICT-driven pedagogy improved learners' performance. From the analysis of TAM constructs, the study found that 70.8% of the Experimental Group held positive perception toward ICT-

driven pedagogy. Positive attitude toward ICT-driven pedagogy by learners translated into learners encouraging for the adoption of ICT-driven pedagogy.

Wenglinsky (1998) used UbD teaching approach and National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) achievement data to investigate the relationship between the various uses of technology and achievement in Mathematics of U.S Grade 8 learners. In Wenglinsky's (1998) study knowledge and skills were taught in the context of helping learners to achieve the desired understanding and to thoughtfully apply their knowledge to authentic problems. Wenglinsky (1998) found a significant relationship between the NAEP test scores and the use of technology that focused on mathematical projects, problems and simulations that promoted application of knowledge and higher order thinking. He also found that when computers were used for higher-order thinking skills, learners performed better and so suggested that teachers focus on using computers to apply higher order skills learned elsewhere in class. Hence, in this study, ICT tools such as GSP and videos were used to promote higher-order thinking skills, i.e. deeper understanding through the use of visuals and geometrical proofs. Learners were tested on whether they had achieved higher order thinking skills through discussion questions, lesson presentation and using post-test results.

Hanna and Remington (1996) found that color, as a stimulus, is a part of memory representation or as imaginary. Mishra, in a pilot study of 161 students

taking a General Psychology Course, found that students performed better (roughly 4 percentage points) with PowerPoint presentations as opposed to lectures with overhead transparencies, and the liked PowerPoint better than transparencies .Lowry (1999), in a study of 390 students enrolled in three sections of an Environmental Science course, found an 8% point increase in the students in the PowerPoint cohorts. Lowry did not give the same test to all three sections, only in the same format of the test, the students preferred PowerPoint over transparencies.

According to Osunade (2003) internet is a valuable source of information for students looking for ideas for project and assignments. Supporting this, Agommuoh and Nzewi (2003) believed that secondary students who are exposed to video-based instructions in science had significantly better results than those who were taught using 48 the lecture method. It is against this background of looking at ICT as a medium of instruction in teaching and learning in secondary schools that this study is conceived. Therefore, the study is an attempt to establish through a statistical model the impact of ICT on teaching and learning of mathematics in secondary schools. According to Gbamanja, (1989. p. 131), education is a process, which seeks to change the behavior of a learner. Overall, behaviorist view education as the process of changing the behavioral pattern of people. Behavior in this sense refers to the way we change the learner, his or her

thinking, his or her feelings and his other overt actions (Hergenhahn and Olson 1997).

Thus education is the process by which society deliberately transmits its cultural heritage through schools, colleges, universities and other institution (Gbemanja 1989). In other to achieve the above- mentioned purpose in education, information and communication technology (ICT), one could argue is an essential ingredient that could help bring these gains and benefits to the learners. Realistically, several researchers admitted that ICT have an impact in learning and teaching of science. Globally, the use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) is fast gaining prominence and becoming one of the most important elements defining the basic competencies of student. In Nigeria, science teaching at that various level still retains the old conservative approach and if this situation would change, there is need for a diagnostic study that this research offers.

Nicole (2009) analyzed the performance and attitudes of technical writing students in PowerPoint-enhanced and in non-PowerPoint Lectures. Four classes of 46 upper level undergraduates (n = 84) at a mid-sized, Southern University taking a one semester technical writing course were surveyed at the beginning and end of the course about their perceptions of PowerPoint. Of the four sections, two classes were instructed using traditional lecture materials (teacher at podium, chalkboard,

and handouts); the other two sections were instructed with PowerPoint presentations. All four classes were given the same pre- and post-test to measure performance over the course of the semester. Traditional lecture or PowerPoint presentations consisted of at least 50% of the course, with the remaining time spent on exercises and small group work. Results revealed that while most students preferred PowerPoint, performance scores were higher in the sections with the traditional lecture format which could be the effect of variables uncontrolled.

The study of Bartsch and Cobern (2003) noted that students preferred PowerPoint over the use of TOHP, but that in some instances the content of the PowerPoint presentation distracted students and they performed less well on tests compared with a control group. Szabo and Hastings (2000) carried out an extensive study comparing PowerPoint and OHP and observed no difference in student performance in tests. The most important factor was lecture subject difficulty in determining the students' performance in these tests. They concluded that the efficacy of using PowerPoint was case specific rather than universal.

Again, Blokzijl and Naeff's (2004) surveyed 69 Dutch students' reactions to PowerPoint as a tool and to lectures using PowerPoint instead of overhead transparencies. These students preferred PowerPoint over transparencies and liked the slides with large font sizes, unity in layout, and easy-to view color contrasts.

Not surprisingly, these are the same features that teachers and authors emphasize when teaching effective PowerPoint presentations.

Nouri and Shahid (2005) conducted a study to test whether using PowerPoint in an accounting course enhanced student short-term memory, long-term memory, and 45 attitudes toward class presentation and the instructor. An experiment was conducted which includes a treatment-control design, in a classroom setting throughout a semester. In one section of an accounting principles II (Managerial Accounting) course, PowerPoint was used as the delivery system, while the second section was taught using the traditional delivery system. The results showed that Power-Point presentation may improve student attitudes towards the Instructor and class presentation. The results did not provide conclusive evidence that PowerPoint presentations improved short-term or long-term memory. The latter results are consistent with other media comparison studies that show the medium alone does not influence learning.

Apperson, Laws, and Scepanisky (2006) showed that college students enrolled in classes in which the professors used PowerPoint with lectures reported more interest in the class, an easier time paying attention, and greater learning when compared to the same classes in which the same professors used only chalkboards. Nouri and Shahid (2008), conducted a study to explore whether providing lecture notes when Power Point is used for class presentation affected

student performance and attitudes toward instructor. This study was conducted in a classroom setting throughout the semester. The experiment involved two sections of an Accounting Principles I course. The results showed that students who did not receive PowerPoint lecture notes indicated that the instructor was more effective and efficient than students who received PowerPoint lecture notes. No differences were found between the two groups in evaluating the instructor on such attributes as preparedness, caring about students and feedback. The results further indicated that providing lecture notes did not appear to affect the performance.

Ogdol and Lapinid (2013) used UbD lesson plan in order to develop learners' mathematical understanding on linear equations in two variables; the study also investigated learners' perceptions of their skills and proficiency before and after the implementation of the UbD lesson plan. UbD lesson plan was validated by eleven professional teachers. The study was carried out in a heterogeneous class of 40 learners in a private laboratory school in Manila. Learners were assessed using written exercises and performance task. The data was analyzed using z-statistic. After the implementation of the UbD lesson plan, the researcher found UbD unit plan or the backward curriculum to have led to the development of above 70% learners' mathematical understanding. The researchers also found that UbD positively affected learners' perceptions which lead to better performance in the subject content. Therefore, Ogdol and Lapinid (2013)

recommended the employment of the Understanding by Design framework in teaching Mathematics at all levels of learning. Although, Ogdol and Lapinid's (2013) study did not incorporate technology their study findings assisted in explaining the effectiveness of the UbD approach.

The following section discusses the theoretical framework that informed this study in terms of learners' perceptions of ICT-driven pedagogies.

2.4 Effects of GSP on academic performance

A qualitative study was conducted in Namibia on Geometry by Mateya (2008) using Van Hiele' Theory in order to analyze geometrical conceptualization of Grade12 learners. Mateya (2008) found that most of the learners had a weak conceptual understanding of geometric concepts and the majority could competently operate below Level 3 of the Van Hiele Theory. Further, Mateya (2008) recommended that the teaching and learning of Geometry should involve more hands-on activities that would enhance learners' conceptual understanding of geometric concepts. Furthermore, correct spelling and pronunciation of geometrical terms should be used at all times. In addition, Mateya's findings were used to inform the development of the first lesson plan with respect to how the learners understood the geometrical concepts as required to achieve the basic competencies stated in the syllabus

Another study was carried out by Idris (2009) on the impact of using Geometers' Sketchpad (GSP) on Malaysian learners' achievement and Van Hiele Geometric thinking. The researcher used GSP and the Van Hiele Theory to describe and identify stages that learners went through as they moved from a holistic perception of geometric shapes to a refined understanding of geometric proof. The study had 32 learners as an Experimental group and 33 as a Control group, and before the intervention, the researchers found no statistically significant difference between the pre-test Geometry performances of the Control and Experimental group. After intervention, Idris (2009) found a statistically significant difference between post-test Geometry performances of learners who had been taught using GSP and those who were not. Further, in the post-test, the Control group exhibited a mean of 13.08 whilst the Experimental group had a mean of 19.65. Idris (2009) recommended the use of Geometers' Sketchpad as an effective tool in teaching and learning Geometry at secondary school level.

A similar study was conducted by Myers (2009) using GSP and Florida Comprehensive Assessment Test (FCAT) to investigate the effect of technology on Grade 10 learners' achievement in Geometry, interaction with gender and socio-economic status and their Van Hiele levels. Myers' (2009) study found a significant difference between the Control and Experimental groups. The researcher recommended the use of technology (particularly GSP) since the

software enhanced understanding and improved learners' Mathematics test scores. It must be noted that, the Van Hiele Theory was not used in this study, but the findings obtained in the studies described in this section helped in the understanding of the achievement levels of SSII.

2.5 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

TAM places emphasis on the behavior of an individual towards the use of ICT. According to Park (2009), TAM is one of several widely used models and it has shown great potential in explaining and predicting individuals' beliefs toward ICT. It postulates that a user's adoption of the new ICT tools is determined by that user's Intention to Use (ITU) them, which in turn is related to the user's beliefs about them (Chandra, Theng, O'Lwin, & Foo, 2009). TAM is built on two fundamental elements, which are: Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use (Al-Adam, Al-Adam, & Smedley, 2013).

Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) signifies attitudes and behavioral intention to accept technology. PEOU can be defined as the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular technology would be free of effort, meanwhile PU is defined as the degree to which an individual believes that using a particular technology would enhance his/her performance (Davis, 1989). Consequently, the more an individual perceives the technology as easy to use or useful, the greater the chances he/she is willing to adopt or

recommend it be used. Dahawy and Kamel (n.d.) agree that the easier the technological tool was used, the more it was adopted and the more it was being used to communicate information. Individuals are more likely to have a positive attitude on the use of a new technology if they perceive that it is easy to use and it is useful.

2.6 Perception of Learners on ICT-driven Pedagogy

Instructions delivered and/or learned through ICT tools are perceived by many authors as significant in improving teaching and learning (Passey, Rogers, Machell, McHugh, & Allaway, 2003; Hartsell, Herron, Fang, & Rathod, 2010; Banyard, Underwood, Kerlin, & Stiller, 2011). The use of ICT tools in classrooms instills a sense of responsibility in learners, making them realise their role in education and helping them understand difficult concepts. Passey et al. (2003) argued that the use of ICT has a positive impact on the motivational level of learners in school subjects and on learners' perceptions toward subjects and schooling, thus influencing them to perform well in school subjects. In addition, Slouti and Barton (2007) argued that the use of ICT in teaching and learning has a positive impact on learners' perceptions of Mathematics, and it accounts for better performance.

Perceptions are an important aspect in social judgments, behaviors and the decision making process. They can either be negative, positive or neutral. In a

study carried out by Idris (2009) on the impact of using GSP on Malaysian learners' achievement and Van Hiele Geometric thinking, using a 5 point Likert scale; Idris (2009) determined perceptions of learners towards the use of GSP. Most of the learners showed positive perceptions and felt that GSP made them comfortable learning Mathematics.

In another study, by Omollo, Indoshi and Ayere, (2013) on attitudes of learners toward the use of ICT in the implementation of Biology curriculum, calculated the mean, standard deviation and t-test in order to establish the perception levels of learners. A mean score of 3.5 and above was interpreted to denote a positive attitude, between 2.5 and 3.5 neutral and below 2.5 negative. The study found that learners had a positive attitude towards the use of ICT, however no significant difference was found between gender and attitude ($\alpha = 0.05$, $t = -1.138$). Learners' attitudes are one of the determinant factors for the use of ICT approaches in teaching and learning. This study adopted the mean scores (see Section 3.11 under Methodology) obtained in Omollo et al. (2013) in order to categorize learners' perceptions of ICT-driven pedagogy.

2.7 Summary of the Literature

This chapter presented the development of the conceptual framework from the literature. The chapter covered Bruner's Constructivist views on the effects of teaching and learning with technology, UbD teaching approach, UbD Backward

design process and facets of understanding which are used as assessment objectives. The chapter also presented research findings that were carried out on academic performance and ICT driven teaching strategies. The researchers looked at the TAM and cognitive absorption that explain learners' perceptions toward ICT adoption in teaching. Literature revealed that studies on ICT-driven pedagogy and Geometry in Nigeria are nonexistent; in addition literature on UbD is limited in the developing countries.

Thus, literatures from other parts of the world were used as a basis to explain impacts of ICT-driven pedagogy on the performance and to understand learners' perceptions toward ICT-driven pedagogy in Nigeria, particularly in Gombe local government.

The next chapter discusses the methodology used to collect data for this study.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This section presents the research methods adopted for the study. It explains the research design, the population of the study, the sample size and sampling technique, sources and methods of data collection, techniques for data analysis and variables of the study and their measurements data analysis and procedures were discussed.

3.1 Research design

This study is an experimental because it involved two groups (Experimental and control group) where one was treated using the traditional method and the other was treated using special ICT intervention method.

3.2 Population

The population of the study comprised of all SS2 students in Public Schools in Gombe local government area of Gombe State. There are 16 Public senior secondary schools in Gombe local government with a total of 14230 students enrolled in to SSII. (Gombe State Ministry of Education, 2018).

3.3 Sample and sampling procedures

Four schools was purposely selected to represent the 16 schools, because they are up to 30% of the schools, on the basis that the school was one of those that

have well equipped computer laboratory. Random probability sampling was also used to select the participants in each of the SS2 classes of the selected schools to form a group. School A had a computer laboratory and Geometers' Sketchpad (GSP) software was installed to each computer by the researcher. It served as an Experimental Group on the basis that it had GSP software. The other formed the control group.

3.4 Research instruments

Mathematics pre-test and post-test questions was set up based on the curriculum of the schools on geometry. These questions were constructed by the researcher. There are 11 questions which carry 15 marks. The pre-test and post-test is aimed at testing learners' knowledge and understanding on Geometry topics before and after the intervention respectively. The sample of the test items are in the Appendix of the research.

3.5 Instructional material

The instructional materials of this research include geometer's sketch pad software, computers, math sets, projector, e.t.c.

3.6 Validity

This study relied on face, content and constructs validity procedures to establish whether the instruments measured what they were supposed to measure

(Cohen, Manion, & Morrison, 2011). In order to measure face and content validity of the research instruments, they were assessed by an expert in the research content area at Gombe state university. The purpose was to avoid unclear questions, vocabulary and sentence structures that might be too difficult, poorly constructed items, improper arrangements of items and ambiguous test items which were inappropriate for the outcomes to be measure.

3.7 Pilot Testing

Pilot study was conducted in order to ascertain feasibility of conducting the present study. Content and face validating were taken care of and provided ground for the real study. The reliability coefficient of 0.86 was found significant. The findings enabled the researchers to fine tune the instrument and adjust the set time of the test with extra 10 minutes. They equally made provision for power generator to bridge the gaps experienced during the study. IQMIC community secondary school Gombe, SS II students were used for the pilot study. The pilot study involves a group that has the same characteristics with the research sample, but not necessarily involved in the main study (Angrist and Lavy, 2004).

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

The Geometry Performance Test (GPT) composed of 10 items in various difficulty levels from five areas of senior secondary school geometry was used and had reliability coefficient of 0.86 using split-half (odd-even) method. In this

method the score obtained from each individual was divided into two groups by pooling the odd number items and even number items, ranking them and obtained the sum of the squares of the deviation of the ranks. Spearman-Brown prophecy method was applied to find out the coefficient of reliability from the comparable values of the post-test at 0.5% levels of significance (see Appendix)

3.9 Data collection procedures

The data for this research was collected from the tests conducted to the participants before and after the experiment. The scores of the two secondary schools were considered for analysis. Mathematics pre-test was administered to the two groups the day before the commencement of treatment and the results of the individual learners were recorded for analysis. Teaching was carried out for one day due to lack of enough time on school days from 11:00am – 1:00pm. The post-test was conducted immediately after completion of the treatment of each group. The teaching process was pictured. The pictures are on the Appendix of this research.

3.10 Data Analysis

Microsoft Excel was used to present the data in tabular form and the package was used to calculate the mean of the tests (pre-test and post-test) given to each group as well as the range of the scores. The mean of the scores of the tests was compared to see whether there is significant difference or not.

3.11 Ethical Consideration

First, the researcher obtained an introductory letter from the project coordinator of the department of Education of the Gombe state university to the Principals of the schools for permission to conduct the study. The sample of the introductory letter is in the Appendix of the study. Second, learners participating in the study were informed about the purpose and objectives of the study for them to participate voluntarily. In addition, learners' attendance record was kept, although the names of the learners were not revealed and each participant was assigned a code. They were assured that the information obtained from them would be for research purposes only and would be treated with utmost confidentiality.

CHAPTER FOUR

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.0 Introduction

The chapter presents the results and discussion of the findings of the data collected from the pre-tests and post-tests in an attempt to answer the research questions.

4.1 Biographic Information of Learners

A sample of 20 learners of SSII level from two public schools (School A and School B) in the Gombe local government, participated in this study. The scores of the tests are shown in the Tables below.

4.2 Presentation of Results

This section presents the result of the study as follows.

Research question 1 states that what is the background knowledge of Senior Secondary School students in Geometry both experimental and control group prior to the treatment? The test that is related to this research question is the pre-test of both the groups (Experimental and Control). This is shown in Table 1 and Table 2 as follows.

4.2.1 School A (Control group) Pre-test

Table 1:

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Participant Code</i>	<i>Score</i>
1	C01	1
2	C02	0
3	C03	1
4	C04	1
5	C05	1
6	C06	0
7	C07	0
8	C08	0
9	C09	0
10	C10	1

$$\text{Mean} = 0.5$$

Table 1 above shows the scores of the pre-test of the control group. The students failed woefully as mean of the scores is 0.5 and the range of the scores is 1.

4.2.2 School B (Experimental group) pre-test

Table 2:

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Participant Code</i>	<i>Score</i>
1	E01	0
2	E02	1
3	E03	2
4	E04	1
5	E05	0
6	E06	1
7	E07	0
8	E08	0

9	E09	2
10	E10	2

Mean = 0.9

Table 2 above shows the scores of the pre-test of the experimental group. They also failed woefully in the pre-test as the mean of the scores is 0.9 and the range is 2.

Research question 2 states that what is the effect of ICT-Driven pedagogy on Senior Secondary School students' (experimental group) academic achievement in geometry? The test that is related to this question is pre-test and the post-test scores of the experimental group as shown in Table 2 above and Table 3 below.

4.2.3 School B (Experimental group) post-test

Table 3:

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Participant Code</i>	<i>Score</i>
1	E01	5
2	E02	7
3	E03	12
4	E04	4
5	E05	8
6	E06	10
7	E07	2
8	E08	5
9	E09	9
10	E10	9

Mean = 7.1

Table 3 above shows the scores of the post-test of the experimental school. They performed wonderfully higher than that of their pre-test with the mean of the scores as 7.1 and the range as 10.

Research question 3 states that what is the mean gain of Senior Secondary School Students in Geometry after the treatment? The test that is related to this research question is the post-test of the control group and the post-test of the experimental group as shown in Table 3 above and Table 4 below.

4.2.4 School A (Control group) Post-test

Table 4:

<i>S/N</i>	<i>Participant Code</i>	<i>Score</i>
1	C01	7
2	C02	4
3	C03	6
4	C04	5
5	C05	1
6	C06	6
7	C07	6
8	C08	7
9	C09	7
10	C10	

Mean = 5.444444

Table 4 above shows the scores of the post-test of the control group. The performance is higher than that of their pre-test with the mean as 5.44 and the range of 6.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The following are the discussion of the results based on the data collected during the research treatments by the researchers.

With reference to the data presented in Table 1, the mean of the score is 0.5 and the range is 1. Comparing these with the data presented in Table 2, which gives the mean of 0.9 and the range of 2. The difference in the mean score is 0.4 and the difference in the range is 1 (not wide), which not significant enough to differentiate the level of the students in the research. This shows that the background knowledge of Senior Secondary School students in Geometry both experimental and control group prior to the treatment is the same. This has come in line with the Bruner's (1960) Constructivist Theory which states that learning is an active process in which learners construct new ideas or concepts based upon existing knowledge.

Again, going by the data presented in Table 2, which gives the mean of 0.9 and the range of 2 and Table 3, which gives the mean of 7.1 and the range of 10, the difference in mean is 6.2 and the difference in the range is 8. This shows that there is a wide gap between the performances of the learners (experimental group) prior the treatment (in pre-test) and after the treatment (in post-test). This implies that ICT-Driven pedagogy has greater effect on Senior Secondary School students' (experimental group) academic achievement in geometry. This is in agreement

with Wenglinsky (1998) who found that when computers were used for higher-order thinking skills, learners performed better and so suggested that teachers focus on using computers such as GSP and Idris (2009) and Myers (2009) who found a statistically significant difference between post-test Geometry performances of learners who had been taught using GSP and those who were not.

With reference to the result presented in Table 3, which gives the mean of 7.1 and the range of 10, and Table 4, which gives the mean of 5.44 and the range of 6. The difference in the mean is 1.66 and the difference in the range of the scores is 4. This shows that the experimental group gained more than the control group. This is in agreement with Keùan and Çaliùkan (2013) who stated that learners who were taught using traditional methods performed poorly compared to those that were taught using Geometer's Sketch Pad (GSP). It has also come in line with Kanandjebo (2017) who found that there was a statistically significant difference between the two groups (dependent variables and independent variables) in terms of learner performance on geometry topics.

From the discussion above, the research hypotheses were also solved as follows at 0.5 degree of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean academics performance of both experimental and control group at pretest (prior to the treatment).

From the data in Table 1 and Table 2 above, the mean scores of the pretest of the control and the experimental groups are 0.5 and 0.9 respectively, which gives the difference of 0.4 which not significant. Therefore, H_{01} can be accepted.

$(H_{01}: \mu_{control} = \mu_{experimental})$

H_{02} : There is no significant difference in the mean academics performance of experimental group at pretest and post-test (After the treatment).

Also from the data in Table 2 and Table 3 above, the mean scores of the pretest and posttest of the experimental groups are 0.9 and 7.1 respectively, which gives the difference of 6.2 which much significant. Therefore, H_{02} can be rejected.

$(H_{02}: \mu_{control} \neq \mu_{experimental})$

H_{03} : There is no significant difference in the mean academics performance of both Experimental and control group at post-test (After the treatment).

Again, from the data in Table 3 and Table 4 above, the mean scores of the posttest of the control and the experimental groups are 5.4 and 7.1 respectively, which gives the difference of 1.7 which significant enough to reject H_{02} .

$(H_{03}: \mu_{control} \neq \mu_{experimental})$

Therefore, hypothesis H_{01} was accepted while H_{02} and H_{03} were rejected.

4.4 Summary of the major findings

1. Learners construct new idea based on their previous knowledge and their level of understanding.

2. ICT-driven pedagogy has positive effects on the performance of secondary school learners.
3. Learners that were taught using ICT-driven pedagogy gained more than those that were taught using the traditional method.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0 Introduction

This chapter provides a summary of the study; beginning with the research processes and followed by the summary of research findings. It also presents reflections on the study and conclusions drawn from the findings. Finally, based on the research findings this chapter presents recommendations.

5.1 Summary of the research findings

This section presents the key research findings of the study. The findings are presented with reference to the research questions. Literature findings are also discussed to boost the value of the discussion.

5.1.1 Learners' Level of Understanding

In this research, it was found that learners' level of understanding is very important because learners construct new ideas or concepts based upon existing knowledge. The Experimental and Control groups had very closed mean scores in the pre-test prior to the intervention which shows that they are in the same level. Learner's background knowledge contributes more in learning new ideas. It supports Bruner's (1960) constructivist theory.

5.1.2 Effects of ICT-driven Pedagogy on learners performance in geometry

The results of this study suggested positive effects of ICT-driven pedagogy on the learners' performance compared to the performance of those taught using traditional methods of teaching. The Experimental and Control groups had contiguous mean scores in the pre-test prior to the intervention. Further, no significant difference was found between Experimental and Control group. This indication suggests that the two groups were equivalent before the intervention.

After the intervention, the Experimental group had outdone the Control group in the post-test. This supports Wenglinsky (1998)'s findings.

5.1.3 The mean gain of Senior Secondary School Students in Geometry

The result of this study suggested that the experimental group significantly gained more than the control group. This also supports Keuan and Çaliukan (2013) and Kanandjebo (2017).

5.2 Conclusion

This study investigated the impacts of ICT-driven pedagogy on performance of SSII in Geometry in Gombe local government area. It aimed at finding alternative ways to improve learners' performance in Geometry as a result of the massive failure in the SSCE level in mathematics especially in the areas of geometry. The use of ICT-driven pedagogy might improve learner's performance in geometry.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations are made, based on the findings of this study.

1. Teachers should consider the learners' background knowledge before giving them treatment as it enhances understanding of new ideas.
2. Mathematics teachers should be encouraged to use ICT-driven pedagogy when teaching Geometry topics i.e. geometrical terms, relationships, angle properties and symmetry, in order to improve the academic achievement of their learners.
3. Teachers should be encouraged to use visual media in teaching since visual media strengthens understanding by simplifying abstract concepts.

4. Government should provide adequate ICT facilities in all levels of education as it might enhance learning.
5. Schools that are equipped with ICT facilities should be encouraged to secure GSP software in order to enhance teaching and understanding of geometrical terms, relationships, angle properties and symmetry.
6. Further detailed studies should be conducted to investigate the effectiveness of ICT-driven pedagogy on performance of learners in geometry in other areas.

5.4 Suggestions for further studies

The concept of ICT-driven pedagogy is very wide, which makes the researchers unable to touch so many aspects. In view of that, the researchers suggest to whosoever wishes to carry out further study to look into:

1. Further detailed studies should be conducted to investigate the effectiveness of ICT-driven pedagogy on performance of learners in geometry in other areas.
2. A more detailed study should be conducted on the relationship between ICT-driven pedagogy versus gender, perceptions and performance in Geometry; mainly focusing on why females perform better in Geometry topics when taught with ICT-driven pedagogy.

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APPENDIX I

Pre-test and Post-test Items

IMPACTS OF ICT-DRIVE PEDAGOGY ON SSII STUDENTS PERFORMANCE IN SOME SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN GOMBE LGA

PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST ITEMS

Participant Number:

Instructions:

- Do NOT write your name on this paper.
- Answer all questions and show your working.
- Write your answers in the spaces provided after each question.

Section 1:

Use the diagram below to answer the following questions.

1. Line AB is called
2. Line BC is called
3. Which type of triangle is $\triangle ABC$?

Section 2:

Identify the parts in the diagram below.

1. The shaded part of the circle is called
2. The part of the circle that is not shaded is called
3. The curve XYZ is called
4. The curve XZ is called

Appendix II

Pre-test and Post-test Items 2

Section 3:

Find the value of x in the figure below. O is the centre.

Solution:

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

Section 3:

Find the values of the lettered angles in the diagram below. Give reason in each.

1. $p = \dots\dots$ Reason.....
2. $q = \dots\dots$ Reason.....
3. $r = \dots\dots$ Reason.....

Total marks = 15 marks

End

Appendix III

Researchers delivering a lecture to the learners using ICT-driven pedagogy

